

Mercury (II) Complexes of Schiff Bases

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A number of mercury (II) complexes of Schiff bases have been isolated and characterised. The structures have also been discussed.

Metal complexes of Schiff bases have been studied for a long time. Stimulating reviews on the synthetic, physicochemical and stereochemical studies of these metal complexes have been published^{1,2}. Although a wide variety of stable chemical species has been synthesised containing both transition and nontransition metals, mention of mercury (II) complexes of Schiff bases in literature is quite scanty. This is possibly due to the closed shell electronic configuration of the metal ion concerned.

A few years ago, Bahr and Coworkers³⁻⁵ described the preparation and properties of a few mercury (II) complexes of Schiff bases derived from diacetyl with aniline, *p*-toluidine and *o*-toluidine and also of Schiff bases derived from pyridine-2-aldehyde with various alkylamines. Recently Bailar⁶ reported the preparation, structure and thermal stability of mercury (II) complexes of bis-(2-pyridinal)-biphenylene-4,4'-diimine.

In continuation of our work on metal complexes of Schiff bases, we attempted to isolate some mercury (II) complexes of the same type of ligands. The present communication describes the preparation and properties of a number of Hg (II) complexes of Schiff bases derived from 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with aniline, anthranilic acid, sulphanilamide, ethylenediamine and orthophenylenediamine and also of Schiff bases derived from 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol with salicylaldehyde, 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and acetylacetone. The mercury (II) complex of salicylaldehyde-ethylenediamine is also included in this paper.

The Schiff bases of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with different mono- and di- amines, aminoacids were prepared as described by Poddar⁷ and those of 1, 3-diaminopropane-2-ol with salicylaldehyde, 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and acetylacetone were prepared according to the method of Dey⁸.

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EXPERIMENTAL

The mercury (II) complexes were prepared by refluxing calculated amount of mercuric chloride and the appropriate Schiff bases in aqueous-ethanol medium on water bath for about two hours. Sodium acetate facilitated the precipitation of mercury (II) complexes in the case of Schiff bases of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with mono-amine and amino acid. All other complexes precipitated out from the reaction mixture during reflux. They were filtered and washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in air.

The mercury (II) complexes are insoluble in water and many common organic solvents. They are soluble in dilute alkali solutions but are decomposed by strong mineral acids on boiling. Table I below shows the elemental analyses, compositions and colour of the compounds isolated.

TABLE I

Name of the complex, colour and composition	Analyses					
	Calculated %			Found %		
	Hg	N	Cl	Hg	N	Cl
(1) 3-aldehydosalicylic acid aniline-Hg (II); yellowish brown; (C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ N) ₂ Hg.	29.47	4.11	—	30.24	4.33	—
(2) 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-anthranilic acid-Hg(II); orange yellow; (C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅ N) ₂ Hg	26.10	3.61	—	25.98	3.25	—
(3) 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-sulfahilamide-Hg(II) brown; (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₂ S) ₂ Hg	23.92	6.67	—	23.52	6.72	—
(4) 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-ethylenediamine-Hg(II) yellowish brown; (C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂) ₂ Hg	36.16	5.05	—	35.94	4.86	—
(5) 3-aldehydosalicylic acid orthophenylenediamine-Hg(II) red-rose; (C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂) ₂ Hg	33.29	4.64	—	32.87	4.08	—
(6) Bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylene-diamine-Hg(II); yellow; (C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ Hg	42.98	6.00	—	43.20	6.09	—
(7) 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol-salicylaldehyde-Hg(II); yellow; (C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ Hg)HgCl	54.83	3.82	4.85	55.09	3.73	5.12
(8) (C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂) ₂ Hg	40.39	5.64	—	41.23	6.22	—
(9) 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol-3-aldehydosalicylic acid Hg(II); brown; (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₂ Hg)HgCl	48.94	3.41	4.33	49.11	3.22	4.01
(10) (C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₂) ₂ Hg	34.32	4.79	—	35.21	5.01	—
(11) 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol-acetylacetone-Hg(II); yellowish brown; (C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ Hg)HgCl	58.33	4.07	5.16	57.93	3.73	4.98
(12) (C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂) ₂ Hg	44.32	6.18	—	44.89	6.22	—

DISCUSSION

The Schiff bases of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with mono-amines or amino acids were found^{7,9} to behave as tridentate ligands with acidic group of the amino-component (where

present) remaining free, while those with diamines behave as quadridentate ligands with both the carboxylic groups of the 3-aldehydoacid remaining unattached :

WHERE, R = C₆H₅ ; C₆H₄COOH;
C₆H₄SO₂NH₂

WHERE, R = -(CH₂)₂ , or
-C₆H₄-

It appears from the elemental analyses of the mercury (II) complexes that the Schiff bases of the former group behave as bidentate ligands with the carboxyl groups of both the 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and the amino acids remaining free, which probably accounts for the solubility of the complexes in dil. alkali solutions.

Schiff base of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with ethylenediamine behaved as tetradentate ligand as observed earlier (*loc.cit.*), and the mercury(II) complexes are soluble in dil. alkali solutions.

As already suggested for the transition metal ions⁸, the Schiff bases of 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol with salicylaldehyde, 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and acetylacetone behaved as tetradentate ligands with mercury (II) ions also. But the elemental analyses of their Hg (II) complexes showed metal-ligand ratio as 2:1. Further, on treatment of the water suspension of each of the Hg (II) complexes of the above Schiff bases with KI solution; a transient red colouration was formed which ultimately gave a greenish yellow solution (with excess of KI solution) with the separation of a yellow crystalline compound. The yellow products, just mentioned, were identified as [Hg (II) S.B], where SBH₂ is a molecule of the Schiff base derived from 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol with salicylaldehyde, 3-aldehydosalicylic acid or acetylacetone.

The above observations may be explained by assuming that each Schiff base molecule in these metal chelates is also associated with one HgCl radical by displacing a hydrogen atom in the free hydroxyl group in the otherwise coordinated ligand molecules, and the resultant complex has the following structure (taking the Schiff base of 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol salicylaldehyde as an example) :

The mercury-oxygen bond thus formed in the above complex is not so strong as mercury-nitrogen bond^{10(a,b)} and as such the $> \text{CHO.HgCl}$ group may easily be affected by KI solution producing $\text{K}_2(\text{HgI}_4)$ and $[\text{Hg}(\text{II}) \text{SB}]$.

From the view point of simple ionic theory it seems reasonable that in complex formation large ions like $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ should have high coordination number. Octahedral complexes of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ should, therefore, be comparatively more common, but they are hardly encountered in literature. On the contrary, the tetrahedral complexes of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ are frequently reported¹¹⁻¹⁵.

It appears from the results of the present study that the $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complexes of the Schiff bases under consideration are tetrahedral having sp^3 -hybrid bonds, although polymeric structures of the complexes cannot be completely ruled out as the complexes are highly insoluble and non-volatile. It is not unlikely that even in the polymeric form of the compounds $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ ions possesses tetrahedral configuration^{6,16}.

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